

ISic1453

I.Sicily inscription 1453

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

(yellow)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Selinunte, Baglio Florio
Selinunte

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Κρᾶτις

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284898

EDR 112429

EDCS 41300066

EDCS 64800243

PHI 175678

Bibliography

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à

l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 58 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 82

Arena, R. 1996. Iscrizioni Greche Archaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. Iscrizioni di Sicilia. I. Iscrizioni di Megara Iblea e Selinunte. Pisa. At no.19

Brugnone, A. 2006. Note epigrafiche selinuntine. *Thalassa*. 3: 45-123. At A13 tav.11.53

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1453. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354070>